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РАЗВИТИЕ И СТРУКТУРА ЛИНГВИСТИКИ НА СОВРЕМЕННОМ ЭТАПЕ

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THE DEVELOPMENT AND STRUCTURE OF LINGUISTICS AT THE PRESENT STAGE

Аннотация:

Данная статья посвящена вопросу развития и структуры современной лингвистики. Рассматриваются основные задачи и направления различных областей данной науки. Подчеркивается важная роль лингвистики в описании, изучении и объяснении многих языковых явлений, присущих современному языку.

Лингвистика изучает развитие языка, его явления, составляющие тот или иной язык элементы и единицы. Лингвистика имеет немало языковых разделов, и с каждым годом их становится все больше и больше.

Abstract:

his article is devoted to the development and structure of modern linguistics. The main tasks and directions of various fields of this science are considered. The important role of linguistics in the description, study and explanation of many linguistic phenomena inherent in modern languages is emphasized.

Linguistics studies the development of language, its phenomena, the elements and units that make up a language. Linguistics has many language sections, and their number is growing every year.

Ключевые слова: наука; языкознание; лингвистика; аспект; подход; исследование; область; функция языка.

Key words: science; linguistics; aspect; approach; research; area; function of language.

Modern linguistics is the result of a long historical development of linguistic knowledge. The initial elements of knowledge about language, formed in the course of activity, are associated with the creation and improvement of writing, teaching, compilation of dictionaries, interpretation of sacred texts and texts of old monuments, development of sound speech models. But gradually the range of tasks expanded, the analysis was subjected to an increasing number of aspects of language, the construction of a new linguistic discipline, formed new research methods. Thus, today linguistics is a system that unites many linguistic sciences that give us fairly complete knowledge of all aspects of human language as a whole and all individual languages.

Linguistics covers a number of subfields. An important current division is the study of the structure of language (grammar) and the study of meaning (semantics). Grammar includes morphology, syntax, and phonology. Semantics, the study of the meaning of words (lexical semantics) and fixed phrases (phraseology), and how they combine to form the meanings of sentences. Phonetics is a related branch of linguistics concerned with the actual properties of speech sounds, non-speech sounds, and how they are produced and perceived. Pragmatics, the study of how utterances are used (literally, figuratively, or otherwise)

in communicative acts. Discourse analysis, the analysis of language use in texts (spoken, written, or signed).[5]

There are many areas of modern linguistics, some dominated by one or other theoretical approach: evolutionary linguistics attempts to explain the origins of language; historical linguistics studies language change; and sociolinguistics examines the relationship between language variation and social structures.

Linguistics, like other sciences, draws on work in areas such as psychology, computer science, philosophy, biology, human anatomy, neuroscience, sociology, anthropology, and acoustics.

Linguistics is concerned with describing and explaining the nature of human language. This includes questions about what is universal about language, how language can change, and how people learn languages. All humans acquire competence in whatever language is spoken around them as they grow up, with the obvious need for explicit, conscious learning. Linguists therefore assume that the ability to acquire and use language is an innate, biologically based capacity in modern humans, like the ability to walk. However, it is generally accepted that no major genetic differences underlie the differences between languages: an individual acquires whatever language(s) he or she encounters in childhood, regardless of ancestry or ethnicity.[1]

Many linguists believe that these distinctions overlap to a large extent, and the independent significance of each of these areas is not universally accepted. Regardless of the position of any particular linguist, each area has core concepts that contribute to significant scientific research.

Much modern linguistic research, particularly within the generative grammar paradigm, has been devoted to attempts to explain the differences between the world's languages. This has worked on the assumption that if human linguistic abilities are narrowly constrained by human biology, then all languages must share certain fundamental properties.

Similarities between languages may have several different sources. At their simplest, universal properties may be due to universal aspects of human experience. Arguments for language universals also come from documented cases of sign languages developing in communities independently of spoken languages. The properties of these sign languages generally correspond to many of the properties of spoken languages.

The study of languages at a particular point in time (usually the present) is "synchronous", while diachronic linguistics studies how language changes over time, sometimes over centuries. It has both a rich history and a strong theoretical foundation for the study of language change.

Contextual linguistics may involve the study of linguistics in interaction with other academic disciplines. Interdisciplinary fields of linguistics look at how language interacts with the rest of the world.

Sociolinguistics, anthropological linguistics, and linguistic anthropology are seen as fields that bridge the gap between linguistics and society at large.

Psycholinguistics and neurolinguistics link linguistics with the medical sciences.

Other interdisciplinary fields of linguistics include evolutionary linguistics, computational linguistics, and cognitive science.[2]

Linguists are primarily concerned with finding and describing commonalities and variations both within individual languages and across all languages. Applied linguistics takes the results of this research and applies them to other fields. The term "applied linguistics" is often used to refer to the use of linguistic research only in language teaching, but the results of linguistic research are used in many other fields. Applied linguists focus on understanding and engineering solutions to real-world linguistic problems, rather than simply applying existing technical knowledge from linguistics; they also typically apply technical knowledge from multiple sources, such as sociology (e.g., conversation analysis) and anthropology.

Today, computers are widely used in many areas of applied linguistics. Speech synthesis and recognition use phonetic and phonemic knowledge to provide voice interfaces to computers. Applications of computational linguistics in machine translation, computer-aided translation, and natural language processing are areas of applied linguistics that have come to the forefront. In turn, their influence has influenced the design of

theories of syntax and semantics that are applied within the limitations of computers.

Another area that is receiving much attention at the present stage is communicative linguistics, which studies the processes of interpersonal communication with an emphasis on living natural language, considered as a unity of communicative components - physical, psychological, physiological, social, contextual, etc. The topic of communicative linguistics is the study of language in real processes of interpersonal communication.

Communicative linguistics considers speech acts (statement, request, question, etc.) as a unit of communication, the communicative significance of the structural elements of which (words, phrases, sentences) is manifested in a coherent text (discourse). It is used for the linguistic justification of the communicative teaching method.[3]

Communicative linguistics forms its own specific subject of research, which is the junction of "background knowledge - language system". In other words, communicative linguistics is interested in background knowledge not in itself, but from the point of view of how in a particular linguacultural community background knowledge as a non-verbal component of speech communication is woven into the text of a speech production, what is implied and what is explicated in linguistic communication. In real life, we do not say everything we want to say, and we speak "in hints". As a general principle of linguistic communication, there is the so-called "postulate of mitigation". The main task of communicative linguistics is precisely to find out what and how we hint at in order to express a particular communicative task [4].

The development of communicative linguistics began in the second half of the last century and was determined by both practical, applied tasks and theoretical needs of modern semasiology. The introduction of the concepts of "communicative approach", "function", "content", "meaning" into scientific circulation marked the beginning of the end of these disputes. The communicative approach drew a line under the period of arbitrary division of language.

Modern linguistics is defined by a general communicative-discursive focus, i.e. the desire to overcome the limitations of the immanent analysis of the language system and to orient the analysis towards functional characteristics in connection with the socio-cultural context, the personality of the speaker and the immediate communication situation.

At present, communicative linguistics is represented by several directions, differing both in theoretical prerequisites and in research methods. Communicative linguistics may include such linguistic directions as the theory of speech acts, procedural semantics, communicative syntax, text linguistics, various directions of paralinguistics, the theory of communicative behavior, the theory of speech genres, the theory of intercultural communication.

Most modern linguists assume that spoken (or signed) language is more fundamental than written language because many cultures and speech

communities lack written communication, and people learn to speak and process spoken languages more easily and much earlier than they learn to write.

Nevertheless, linguists agree that the study of written language can be useful and valuable. For studies based on corpus linguistics and computational linguistics, written language is often much more convenient for handling large amounts of linguistic data. Large corpora of spoken language are difficult to create and find, and are typically transcribed and recorded. In addition, linguists have turned to textual discourse, found in various computer-mediated communication formats, as a viable site for linguistic research. Thus, the study of writing systems themselves is also considered a branch of linguistics in any case.[5]

It should be noted that domestic and foreign linguistics is currently developing at a fairly rapid pace and is one of the important social disciplines, since it is becoming not only a science of language, but also a

science that solves problems associated with the daily activities of a person in all spheres of life, i.e. practical tasks aimed at ensuring mutual understanding between people and improving the life of society.

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